

Impact of social media marketing on customers' buying intentions: an empirical evidence from Chinese apparel industry

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Abstract: The aim of the study was to investigate the impact of social media marketing on the purchase intention of Fashion/textile product buyers. It was also aimed at measuring the role of brand loyalty towards purchase intentions of the customers of (1) Lu Thai Textiles and (2) Weiqiao Textiles from customer in Ghuangzhou city, China. In order to achieve the aims of the study, 150 responses were collected through structured personal administered questionnaire with close ended options. Statistical procedures for Social Sciences (SPSS) have been implied for the analysis purposed on the data collected after convinces sampling method. Study found that social media marketing and brand loyalty has significant positive impact on purchase intention of the buyers of the fashion products. This study has been done by the limited number of the customers comprising of two brands only in Guangzhou city, china. Future researchers are advised to conduct same study in other parts of the country by including more variables so the results could be generalized and used at vast level. Marketing managers are also advised to consider social media marketing as an effective tool to influence the customer buying intentions and it can be the technique through which they can be at the abreast of the competition.

Keywords: Social Media, Social Media Marketing, Brand Loyalty, Purchase Intention, SPSS, Bargaining and Textiles.

I. INTRODUCTION:

According to Spiro, Bruce & Brewer, (2017), e-commerce activities in China have been slow as compared to the last years. With the strong commitment of the Chinese government to the e-commerce sector and regional distribution centers established by Alibaba Group, China has become the e-commerce center in Southeast Asia in the coming years. E-commerce merchants in the Asia-Pacific region face fierce competition while everyone struggles to gain market share (Monteiro & Teh, (2017). A digital content company, such as Rev Asia, the largest digital media entity, ranked third after Facebook, and Google, based on Chinese traffic, was recently acquired by the traditional media company Media Prima (Russell, B., 2017). It shows that digital content on the Internet, especially digital content on social media platforms, is rapidly replacing the importance of traditional media, especially in China, which ranks among the top five global social networks. Consumers actively participate in social media platforms to contribute and seek information about products and brands before deciding whether to buy. Social networks can actively use Chinese companies as marketing agents to promote their brands, products or services.

Nielsen, L. (2019) highlighted that “surveys on Global Retail Growth Strategies and Global Retail Loyalty Programs concluded that three in five Chinese consumers enjoy taking the time to find bargains”. He further pointed out that “e-commerce market will continue to flourish as consumers are willing to shop for more new products categories, satisfaction that beyond pricing such as the ease of online payment methods, and express delivery for the products. The allegiance to brands is very important for businesses to sustain the fan base and sustainability”.

However, it may not be the same as Monteiro & Teh, (2017), said that “3 out of 4 online shoppers globally abandon their shopping carts before checking out. Researchers further pointed out that when consumers have more options, the expectations become higher, particularly how they engage with the business and receive their purchase”. Therefore good prices are not the only reason that attracts customers but the service that is to be provided along with the products as customers keep on sharing their experience through comments online which enables new customers to think before buying. This is how social media is becoming more important for the products and services quality feedback.

Figure 1: Social media users worldwide (statista.com, 2020)

Background: When customers' decide to buy, consumers use social networks as a source of product information, such as brands, manufacturers and retailers (Ler, 2014). Purchase decisions are highly influenced by electronic word of mouth on social networking sites. The persuasion of e-word-of-mouth is seen as an opportunity for companies to influence consumer purchasing decisions to influence consumers. Consumers look for the price of a product when they conduct research through the Internet. This is also the experience and expectations that Chinese consumers want (ASEAN Up, 2017).

In the review of existing literature, in recent years, much research has been done on foreign social media marketing, word of mouth and brand loyalty. Although in China, research has been carried out in recent years on other aspects that influence the willingness of consumers to buy (Lim et al., 2016). Therefore, it is very important to further verify the buying behavior of Chinese consumers because the use of social media marketing is increasing day by day as mentioned above and firms need more confirmation that if they are interested to increase their brand loyalty, and generate a repeat sales, what are the most significant part and how social media can influence directly or indirectly the purchase intentions which would ultimately enhance a firm's performance and overall economic cycle (Russell, 2017).

Purchase intentions of the customers are increasing through social media as more and more people are getting involved in the use of high speed internet and cell phone along with updated latest applications (Tan, Ooi, & Goh, 2017) and firms focus on designing social media adverts and other related attractions (Saad, AbdulRahman, & Umadi, 2019).

By investigating the impact of social networks on consumer behavior, this study (conducted in Guangzhou, China) contributed to the existing literature in three ways. As, ASEAN Up (2017) pointed out that "Chinese e-commerce market will continue to flourish as consumers are willing to shop for more new products categories, satisfaction that beyond pricing such as the ease of online payment methods, and express delivery for the products". This is why it is felt that more rigorous research is highly needed in this area where practioners are to be guided that how they can make customer loyalty, what is the role of social media marketing in creating purchase intention and make it more favorable for their business and influence the purchase intention of the customers and finally stand out of the competition. This remained the main motivation and reason for this study.

Textile and apparel industry of China: For textiles and clothing, textiles and clothing brief introduction of basic commodities in developed and developing countries. According to the World Economic Outlook of the International Monetary Fund (2012) and Naing and Fly (2015), there is a gain in developing countries like Pakistan, India, Bangladesh, Vietnam, Indonesia, Cambodia and Myanmar cost advantage developed countries rates due to cheap labor. However, China is no longer available with the appearance of cheap labor. In China, this area has a wealth of experience as world-renowned brands such as "Brooks Brothers, Ralph Cole, Calvin Klein, Alain Delon, Gucci, Polo, Lauren, Adidas, Nike, Iraq Cardiff Saint Laurent, Disney, Reebok, Puma manufacturers, GAP, Oshkosh, Burberry, Ashworth" and so on. These brands are produced by a contract manufacturer and Somerset Bay, West Indies, seeds, Anakku heating are all business abroad (Sheng, 2007). Some brands like H & M, Zara, Gap, Uniqlo, Topshop and always 21, the handle, the wet seal,

Benetton, new look, Esprit, C & A, etc., are considered fast fashion retailers and high response Fashion reasonable prices (Caro y Martinez de Albeniz 2014; lu, 2015).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Social Media: According to Boyd and Ellison (2007), the first social media website was established in 1997 under the name SixDegrees.com. SixDegrees.com allows users to establish a profile and connect with friends by providing a tool that provides a tool that can first log in as a member of SixDegrees.com and send messages to friends. It attracted millions of users, but was unable to sustain it and closed in 2000. The closure is because there is little to do after making contact with friends. However, the introduction of SixDegrees.com made netizens pay attention to online social media. Based on the acceptance of online social networks by Internet users, many community tools began to appear on the site with additional features, such as AsianAvenue, BlackPlanet and MiGente. These sites were created to allow online social media users to generate personal, professional and dating profiles.

Online catalogue: Just as consumers turn to Internet search engines for answers to many questions, they also turn to social media to search for anyone living anywhere in the world. This is a natural result of the fact that many sites have gathered hundreds of millions of members. In fact, the number of members of popular websites is greater than the population of many countries / regions (Kim et al., 2010). Except for Kim et al. (2010) the six uses and benefits of social networks, Hutton and Fosdick (2011) also look at the uses and benefits of social networks through passive to active behavior. Passive social media activities include reading and viewing online. Compared to active activities such as writing, creating videos, and posting to websites, reading and viewing online generally requires less participation and cognitive processing. Consumers are more likely to engage in passive use than active use, mainly because such activities require less conscious effort. Hutton and Fosdick (2011) listed a series of activities on social media, from the most favorable to the most unfavorable.

Branding and brand loyalty: In globalization, many firms are trying to gain new customers and likely to retain them for longer term. In this competitive environment where customers are provided with extensive range and varieties of selections and availability of massive amount of information related to specific variants on their disposal, which make them aware about the services and their functionalities, so it get hard for firms to stop their customers switching to other brands and to make them brand loyal, so here brings up the question that what factors should consider to grab their attention and make them brand loyal. Brands as in tangible resources and also one of the outmost esteemed assets that companies have. Right now, brand loyalty is at the core of the marketing activities.

Purchase intention: Consumers have gone through five stages in their decision-making process, namely, identification of needs, search for information, evaluation of alternatives, purchase and final behavior after purchase (Kotler, 2003). In this sense, the purchase behavior intention can be called a personal awareness plan, which constitutes an effort to implement a specific behavior through personal evaluation and regulation of influence (Eagly & Chaiken, 1994). In addition, it describes the buyback intentions and loyalty, because a person is willing to pay a premium, word of mouth and complaints, which represent five behavioral intentions.

Hypothesis: H1: Social Media Marketing (SMM) has a significant positive impact on the customers' Purchase Intention (PI). H2: Brand loyalty (BL) has a significant positive impact on customers' Purchase Intention (PI). H3: Social Media Marketing (SMM) has a significant positive impact on customers' Brand Loyalty (BL). H4: Brand loyalty (BL) mediates the relationship between Social Media Marketing (SMM) and Purchase Intention (PI).

III. METHODOLOGY:

This study has obtained the qualitative data by selecting samples from customers of two Big brands, namely; (1) Lu Thai Textiles and (2) Weiqiao Textiles to discover the interrelations of factors influencing customers' purchase intention.

Population and sampling: In this study, there is no sampling frame because the target population is names. This sample is known as a subset of the target population, where anyone who made purchase fashion apparel and other fashion garments in Guangzhou, and due to confidentiality, it is unlikely that this study could get a list of data collected from this subset can produce results that promote the entire population (Sekaran, 2003; Zikmund et al., 2010). The estimated number of customers among Chinese apparel industry is not disclosed by any of the firm. Therefore, it has taken up a significant of time to reach all the ten outlets for this study, not to involve all customers due to time and cost constrain. And also, the study is mainly focused on regular buying in the study shopping centers.

This study is conducted with the belief of targeted customers whom are still having branded products will give the best input of brand knowledge they have towards favorite brands. The customers of the said brands were convenient and reliable in approaching this academic research whereby they may not faced the problem of understanding the questionnaires given. This, in turn, will hire the rate of the usable questionnaire for the latter analysis and minimal the failure rate of accuracy. Cluster Area sampling is deemed useful to support this descriptive study in order to ascertain and enable to describe the characteristics of the independent variable dimensions, specifically in Guangzhou. In this study, according to the requirements of Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012), at least 150 sample sizes are required for three study variables. Following the golden rule of Hair et al. (2010), there are at least 100 sample sizes when considering five or less configurations.

Instrumentation: All the variables were assessed by survey through questionnaires (self-administered). One single questionnaire used having different sections where inquiry items were grouped. Each set of questions, will be having instructions at the starting in a very clear manner. This led this research to use the same scales which were measure on a 5 points Likert scale which was ranging from “1” as strongly disagree to to strongly agree as “5”

A set of questionnaire was distributed among the customers who consist of the selected study brands. Questionnaire was a pre-formulated written set of questions whereby the respondents were required to answer within the given options. Personally administered questionnaire were chosen to use in the study as the questionnaire is strictly confined to the group of respondents within the particular geographical area. The main reason of using such approach in the study was the approach enable the accuracy of targeted samples within a shorter period of time. This study has, somehow, create the awareness of customers towards the research topic and consequently motivate them to offer their frank answers. Data collection process has involved the researcher to approach the respondents, particularly to determine their current favorite brand status. Customers who were qualified from the first question and aware of the consensus of taking the questionnaire were then agreed to complete the questionnaire. The criteria listed for the participation was adopted by similar data gathering method as by Chaudhuri & Holbrook (2001).

IV. RESULTS:

Total 210 questionnaires were distributed or the data collection out of which 180 were received back as filled questionnaire. During checking it was found the 21 questionnaires were having problem or wrong filling and missing in fillings. Therefore 159 questionnaires were found correct and usable for the further analysis. Out of 159 I used 150 questionnaires for the analysis purpose. In this was qualified response rate was 53% which is very good as per the intercept approach. A frequency distribution was obtained for all the personal data of 150 respondents. The below description will carefully explain the frequency of demographics characteristics of the said respondents (N=150). An analysis on demographics of respondents participated in the questionnaire revealed that 54.5% of the respondents were male. It is clear that there were no gender domination in all the studied brands. Most of the respondents aged between 31-40 years old with 46.6%, followed by 21-30 years old with 40.2% and the remaining 13.2% consists of respondents aged 41-50 years old. The statistic on the position of respondents may also relate closely with their monthly income. The result showed that more than half (74%) of the respondents earned monthly income ranging from US Dollars 2,000 to 5,000 followed by 13% of respondents demonstrated their income level ranged from Us Dollars 5,001 to 8,000. The result also showed that ten of the respondents earned as highest monthly income ranging from US Dollars 10,000 and above further to this 34% of the respondents were found unmarried/ single while 73% of the respondents were having married status. At the same time 25% of the respondents showed that they are separated (divorced/widows).

Demographics	Details	No	%
Gender	Male	76	51
	Female	74	49
Total		150	100
Age	Below 21 years	11	7
	21-30 years	25	17
	31-40 years	51	34
	41-50 years	38	25

	51-60 years	23	15
	Above 60 years	2	1
Total		150	100
Marital Status	Single	52	35
	Married	73	49
	Divorced/Widow	25	17
Total		150	100
Monthly income (US\$)	Below 2,000	0	0
	2,000-5,000	111	74
	5,001-8,000	20	13
	8,001-10,000	9	6
	10,001 & above	10	7
Total		150	100
Internet Use (years)	Less than 1	0	0
	1 to 5	36	24
	6 to 10	97	65
	11 to 15	15	10
	16 and above	2	1
Total		150	100
Social Media Use	All the time	67	45
	4 - 5 times a week	38	25
	1 - 2 times a week	29	19
	A few times a month	16	11
	Total	150	100

Chinese customers are very much used to use Facebook as social media channel of communication and interaction. This list is followed by LinkedIn and Instagram and further so on. It is further found that female customers in China are found to be higher responsive to the social media platforms as compared to the male customers. There is a very clear gap found between male and female customers' choices.

It is quite evident that the respondents are very much concerned about usage of social media based on their age groups. Youth of China from 20-29 are the respondents who are highly used to have social media as a tool for communication and for the same Facebook is found to be the highly influential social media tool. Other age groups are not that much attractive for the social media. As figure showed people around age of 50 year are almost not using any social media platform. As explained earlier gender wise analysis showed that female Chinese are more active on social media platforms as compared to the male Chinese.

Table 2: Results of the full loading

S/N	Item No	Items	Factor loading
1	SMM1	"Which of the following social media site do you have an account with?"	0.77
2	SMM2	"How often do you use social media?"	0.82
3	SMM3	Are you brand conscious?	0.85
4	SMM4	"Example of brands, etc".	0.73

5	SMM5	"There are many marketing campaigns (advertisements, videos, images, posts, reviews, etc.) by the brand on social media site".	0.81
6	SMM6	"The brand regularly updates its contents (posts, pictures, videos, etc.)".	0.79
7	SMM7	"The contents (posts, pictures, videos, reviews, etc.) are relevant to me".	0.71
8	SMM8	"The contents (posts, pictures, videos, reviews, etc.) are popular among friends or others".	0.82
9	BL1	"The brand uses applications (mobile apps) and different platform (social media, website, email, SMS, telephone, etc.) in promoting their products and services".	0.77
10	BL2	"When I need to buy a product/service, my first thought is this brand".	0.71
11	BL3	"I feel secure when I buy this brand because I know that this brand will never let me down".	0.73
12	BL4	I am willing to spend more time and to pay more if I am satisfied with this brand.	0.72
13	BL5	I feel loyal to the brand because they regularly offer rewards (discounts, free gifts, etc.) to engage with me.	0.78
14	PI1	I feel a commitment to continue booking this brand.	0.87
15	PI2	I feel loyalty to this brand.	0.86
16	PI3	I intend to purchase this product/brand again.	0.82
17	PI4	I plan to purchase this brand in future.	0.75
18	PI5	I will encourage friends and relatives to stay this brand.	0.82
19	PI6	I will say positive things about this brand to other people.	0.81
20	PI7	If people asked me, I would strongly recommend that they stay in this brand.	0.76
21	PI8	Booking with this brand in the future would be a wise choice for me.	0.74

Component	Questions	Cronbach's Alpha
Social Media Marketing	"SMM1, SMM2, SMM3, SMM4, SMM6, SMM7, SMM8"	0.707
Brand Loyalty	"BL1, BL2, BL3, BL4, BL5"	0.796
Purchase Intention	"PI1, PI2, PI3, PI4, PI5, PI6, PI7, PI8"	0.832

Regression method has been implied for the measurement of the hypothesis having direct relationships. For the same H1, H2 & H3 results have been obtained. The non-standardized coefficient (B) to predict purchase intention according to social media marketing variables is 0.464; the standardized coefficient (β) is 0.363; the level of significance (signature) is .000. This shows that for every one percent increase in social media marketing, purchase intent is expected to increase by 2,481. From the coefficients, the T value is 5.49 (sig = 0.000), which shows that social media marketing has a positive effect on purchase intention when confidence is 99%.

$$\text{Purchase intention} = 2.017 + 0.464 (\text{SMM}) + 0.085$$

According to the above formula, when the social media marketing is zero, the purchase intention (dependent variable) is equal to 2,017. Therefore, if 1 unit is added to social media marketing, the dependent variable is expected to increase by 0.464 units. The formula is as follows:

The analysis of variance shows that $F(1,198) = 57,154$ (p value <0001) is significant. This shows that brand loyalty can significantly predict purchase intent. The non-standardized coefficient (B) to predict purchase intention based on the brand loyalty variable is 0.521; the standardized coefficient (β) is 0.473; the level of significance (signature) is .000. This shows that for every one percent increase in social media marketing, purchase intentions are expected to increase by 2,362. From the coefficients, the T value of 7.56 ($\text{sig} = 0.000$) shows that brand loyalty has a positive effect on purchase intention with a confidence level of 99%. The general form of the equation for predicting purchase intent based on brand loyalty is as follows:

$$\text{Purchase intention} = 1.841 + 0.521 (\text{brand loyalty}) + 0.069$$

According to the formula above, when brand loyalty is zero, purchase intention (dependent variable) is equal to 1,841. Therefore, if brand loyalty increases by 1 unit, the dependent variable is expected to increase by 0.521 units. According to the social media marketing variables, the non-standardized coefficient (B) to predict brand loyalty is 0.700; the standardized coefficient (β) is 0.658; the level of significance (signature) is 0.000. This shows that for every one percent increase in social media marketing, brand loyalty is expected to increase by 1,788. From the coefficient, the T value of 12.291 ($\text{sig} = 0.000$) shows that social media marketing has a positive effect on lobbying with a 99% confidence level.

$$\text{Brand loyalty} = 1.088 + 0.7 (\text{SMM}) + 0.057$$

According to the formula above, when social media marketing is zero, brand loyalty (dependent variable) equals 1.088. Therefore, if 1 unit is added to social media marketing, the dependent variable is expected to increase by 0.700 units. The equation is as follows: all three hypotheses have a significant impact on purchase intention, and when the p -value <0.001 , all three hypotheses are significant. In short, H1, H2 and H3 are supported.

Summarizing the use of the starter program in SPSS (path "to" from social media marketing to brand loyalty) to test the middleman effect is 0.470, which is significant at a 99% confidence level. Path "b" from brand loyalty to purchase intent is 0.429, which is significant below the 99% confidence level. The total impact of social media marketing on route "c" purchase intent is 0.464, which is significant at a 99% confidence level. For route "c", the influence of social media marketing on purchase intent with brand loyalty as an intermediate variable is 0.262, which is also significant at 99% confidence.

Social media marketing has a significant indirect influence on purchase intention through brand loyalty, with routes and $b = 0.202$, leading confidence interval [0.098, 0.329]. The mediator may represent approximately half of the total effect, $P_m = 0.434$. Assumption four is accepted.

Figure2: Mediating effect

V. DISCUSSION:

The conceptual framework of this study is based on the random brand selection and purchase incidence model modified by Jones and Zufryden (1980). The Jones and Zufryden model considers marketing elements (such as social media

marketing), brand loyalty variables (including demographic variables such as income and number of children in the family) as independent variables, and variables dependents such as purchase intention behavior. However, the conceptual framework of this research treats all aspects of marketing elements and consumer behavior variables such as social media marketing and brand loyalty, and buyback intentions as dependent variables. Suppose that brand loyalty can adjust the relationship between these independent variables and the dependent variables. Although the dependent variable approach used in this study is purchase intention, there is evidence that it is consistent with the results of previous research. Therefore, based on this observation, it can be inferred that regardless of whether the product has been classified, the attributes or determinants used to predict purchase intention, brand selection and buy-back intention are similar.

However, it shows the mediating role of brand loyalty. This may be due to the fact that most consumers already have some knowledge of the product they are going to buy, or it may be due to the fact that, on average, consumers do not trust prior knowledge of the product. The survey results show that on the 5.00 brand loyalty metrics, the mean scores for all consumer categories are between 3.00 and 4.00. Another hypothesis may be that consumers did not make buyback decisions based on past experiences, but were affected by the latest exposure from social media as a source of information and sometimes even used their own when the information was available. Heuristic instinct.

It is better to design the survey for data collection procedures for practical reasons (it was shown to be reasonable in the methodology chapter). However, due to the ease of administration and the large amount of feedback from respondents, there are many other reasons for choosing a survey design. In addition, regarding the length of the questionnaire made up of several pages, the intercepted self-management questionnaire is considered to be the most appropriate. This method is preferred because it gives interviewees sufficient time to answer the questions posed and they volunteer to participate in the survey. In terms of scales and measures, most of these scales are established scales that have been adopted and adapted from past research, with minor modifications to suit the interviewees of this research. It was also observed that for some structures the reliability score and the validity of the scale were consistent with the original scale, and even produced higher scores.

The research tool is a questionnaire, composed mainly of structural questions. The questionnaire is divided into four parts, which are dedicated to answering the objectives related to social media marketing, brand loyalty and consumer buying behavior patterns and demographic information of the respondents. The sampling method used in this study is a non-probability sampling method that uses convenience sampling technology, that is, respondents are divided proportionally according to gender (male and female). Use interception technology to collect data. Frequently visited shopping malls and stores are selected using convenience technologies, including department stores, large supermarkets / shopping centers, supermarkets, and small retail / specialty / discount stores mainly located in downtown Guangzhou. A total of 210 questionnaires were distributed to buyers at these selected locations, of which 180 completed questionnaires were available for analysis.

All in all, this study achieves its goals by establishing a conceptual framework that focuses on different perspectives compared to previous studies, that is, using variables to predict purchase intentions (rather than brand selection and purchasing behavior). . Therefore, this research fills this gap and develops an extended model of consumer behavior, especially purchase intention and the relevant attribute importance variables that explain behavior. Another unique feature and contribution of this research is that it uses a real environment to test the conceptual framework and the contacts with consumers at the exit, unlike previous studies, where most of the latter test performed in inductive experimental environments. . Therefore, this research has made an important contribution to the knowledge system in the context of Chinese consumer behavior. The purpose of this study is to explore the factors that lead to the purchase intention of the Chinese textile and clothing industry. Factors studied include social media marketing, brand loyalty, and purchase intentions.

Conclusion: In the recent research, the result found that the relationship in terms of branding and purchase intention was lacking. And thus, the major strategic and operational emphasis of fashion brands should not be placed solely on the functionality of human resources management, as discussed earlier but also on the service delivery and marketing. In order to increase the level of customers purchase intention, it is crucial for the marketing personals, too, to work extra miles on brand enforcement of the fashion brands. Both customer brand and social media marketing and brand loyalty can only be strengthened if the customers have the in-depth brand knowledge. Carefully selected and knowledgeable customers is to be done in order to ensure that they are constantly acquired full knowledge and understanding of fashion brands values, respectively. This can be further supported by communicating customer satisfaction data as a

feedback system and motivational tool. Do not agree to the perception that customers' brand commitment to their fashion brands is just another external communication exercise by marketing managers. The marketing personnel, on the other hand, are the core professionals to deliver a better service to them. It is also essential to provide these exceptional better products to meet the rivalry from other fashion brands competitors.

The future study that can involve the differentiation among the fashion brands might possibly promote to the brand-building activities. The differentiation among the fashion brands can be further enhanced by engaging brands from other states, for instance, by involving a larger geographical cover area to generalize the critical scenario in China.

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